

Internship Report On
The Role of Travel Agency in Rising of the Culinary Tourism
A Study on Banglalink Travels International Ltd.

Submitted To

Md. Kamrul Hassan

Professor

Department of Tourism and Hospitality Management

Faculty of Business Studies

University of Dhaka

Submitted by

Ispita Nag

Roll: 096, Registration: 2017712244

Department of Tourism & Hospitality Management

Faculty of Business Studies

University of Dhaka

Letter of Authorization

This is to certify that the Internship Report on “The Role of Travel Agency in Rising of the Culinary Tourism- A Study on “Banglalink Travels International” for the degree of Bachelor of Business Administration (BBA) from the Department of Tourism and Hospitality Management, Faculty of Business Studies, University of Dhaka carried out by Ispita Nag, student ID: 096, under my supervision.

This report supports the topic title and fulfills the entire requirements. I have gone through the whole report and found it to be a well-written report. No part of this internship report has been submitted for any degree, diploma, title, or recognition before. I accept this report as the successful completion of the internship program.

I wish every success in her life.

.....

Signature of the Supervisor

MD. Kamrul Hassan

Professor

Department of Tourism and Hospitality Management

Faculty of Business Studies

University of Dhaka

Letter of Transmittal

Date: 07 February 2023

To

MD. Kamrul Hassan

Professor

Department of Tourism and Hospitality Management

University of Dhaka

Subject: Submission of Internship Report entitled “The Role of Travel Agency in the Rise of the Culinary Tourism.

Dear Sir,

With due respect, I would like to inform you that I have submitted a report on The Role of Travel Agency in Rising of the Culinary Tourism: A Study on Banglalink Travel International Ltd. under your active supervision. I hope this report will be informative as well as comprehensive.

To complete this report, I collected the information from authenticated sources and tried my best in terms of analyzing it. I have made my best effort to achieve the objectives of the report study and hope that my effort will serve the purpose. However, I will always be ready to provide further clarification that you may require. So, I request you to kindly accept the report and oblige thereby.

Sincerely yours,

.....

Ispita Nag

ID: 096

THM-11th Batch, B.B.A.

Department of Tourism and Hospitality Management

University of Dhaka

Declaration

I am Ispita Nag, declare that this internship report, entitled “**The Role of Travel Agency in Rising of the Culinary Tourism,**” has been written by me during the year 2023 under the valuable guidance of **MD. Kamrul Hassan**, Professor, Department of Tourism and Hospitality Management, Faculty of Business Studies, University of Dhaka.

The internship report has been completed in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of a Bachelor of Business Administration (BBA) degree. I also declare that the work I have submitted does not infringe upon any existing copyright and that no portion of this internship report has been copied from any degree, diploma, title, or recognition previously obtained.

The information that I have included here is true and original as per my best knowledge, research, and fieldwork, and with possible reference, if any.

.....

Ispita Nag

ID: 096

THM-11th Batch, B.B.A.

Department of Tourism and Hospitality Management

Faculty of Business Studies

University of Dhaka

Acknowledgment

My first thanks go to the Almighty God for giving me the patience and courage to complete this task on time. Next, I'd like to express my gratitude to my internship supervisor, Kamrul, Professor, Department of Tourism and Hospitality Management, University of Dhaka, for providing us with the opportunity and for his constant guidance and support in completing this Internship Report.

This study would not have been possible without the invaluable contributions and unwavering assistance of a number of people who generously offered their expertise and experience to me. During the report preparation, I learned how to prepare a research proposal within a given time period. I have acquired unique knowledge through practical experience, and it will help me in the future to prepare other reports.

Finally, I'd want to express my gratitude to my friends and stakeholders for their kind and helpful collaboration and suggestions throughout the Report's development. They have graciously provided informative comments, useful recommendations, and contributions that have all helped to improve this study.

Executive Summery

Culinary Tourism or Gastronomy Tourism is a modern form of tourism. Culinary experiences of a specific place, country, or people involved with particular and popular culinary activities are now attracting a new base of the tourism market. People now not only want to enjoy a simple luncheon or snacks, but a target segment wants to have a full service covered, Culinary / Gastronomy /Food Tourism.

Operators such as Banglalink Travels International Ltd must seize opportunities in order to fulfil their overall objectives.

In order to succeed in the travel agency business, competitive objectives are created, and competition is never-ending. To achieve the established objectives and be ahead of the market, travel agencies and tour companies are now seeking all possible opportunities. Banglalink Travels International Ltd. makes every attempt to provide excellent service to its loyal clients and to provide them with the most affordable pricing for its products and services. As a consequence, Banglalink Travels International Ltd. has created a brand value in Bangladesh's travel agency industry for its various packages, services, and customer relationship management. Banglalink Travels International Ltd. strives to satisfy its clients by meeting all of their requirements and wants. To guarantee that, they give marketing initiatives a lot of thought. Banglalink Travels International.

The travel and tourism industry is extremely important in our country since it promotes our economic, social, cultural, and political development, as well as creating opportunities for the rise of new forms of tourism in our country. The tour and travel sector is currently one of the world's fastest-growing and biggest industries. Tour and travel organizations should provide such crucial information to potential consumers through various promotional activities in order to excite and draw them to the sponsor's site.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1- Introduction

On behalf of businesses including airlines, railroads, hotels, car rentals, and travel insurance companies, travel agencies offer their clients travel-related services. Today, tourism has impacted people's progress all over the world and is an incredible human development. It has taken root in people's lives quite rapidly. Tourism develops as a result of its sensitivity to the dynamic changes in contemporary human advancement, which contributes to the process of general improvement.

A travel agency's principal job is to serve as an intermediary between the supplier and the consumer, offering travel and tour-related commodities such as airline tickets, bus tickets, and visas. Tourists who reserve hotel rooms and/or ship cabins in advance for a group tour, wedding, or honeymoon do not keep them in the tour and travel industry. A package trip or a ticket is effectively purchased when customers select their packages, and the travel agency typically does not purchase the ticket until the customer expressly demands it. The agency just provided reduced holiday packages and tickets. The price of the tickets and holiday packages that they provide to their customers, as well as the discounted prices that they acquire from suppliers, determine the company's profit. It's known as the commission.

In essence, a travel agency helps clients book tickets and lodging in addition to offering them travel advice and trip information. For marketing their goods to customers, several businesses provide travel brokers a commission. Large travel agencies do this action because they can make more money by selling a thousand trips at a lesser cost than by selling excursions at a higher cost. One of the most significant industries in the world today is the tourist and hospitality sector. Bangladesh makes full use of incredibly advantageous and sufficient conditions for the growth of many forms of tourism. The world's fastest-growing industry right now is tourism. As this industry expands in terms of the number of objectives it seeks to attract visitors, more organizations and associations are getting involved in the transportation, hospitality, and settlement business, offering food and facilities to customers and achieving their goals through customer satisfaction.

1.2- Background of the Study

In Bangladesh, travel companies and tour operators are constantly looking for ways to expand the tourism industry and establish new market niches. Located in CHATTOGRAM, Banglalink Travel International Ltd. is a reputable travel company. They offer a variety of packages to their customers in addition to services like ticketing, hotel reservations, and Hajj packages. They have a sizable market segment of youthful clients who typically purchase packages that contain a variety of services, including hotel reservations, bus and airline tickets, and more. Packages for Banglalink Travels International Ltd.'s clientele typically contain cutting-edge, contemporary travel activities. Numerous contemporary forms of travel are currently generating new market niches for the travel industry.

One distinctive aspect of the evolving modern tourism industry is culinary tourism. There are currently various reasons why people travel. These days, a major factor that draws individuals to travel is their love of eating. Nowadays, a lot of people travel to sample regional cuisine, specialty dishes, etc. Culinary tourism is currently developing in Bangladesh as a fantastic kind of contemporary travel. In addition to Bangladeshis' interest in regional cuisine, the country's indigenous population also frequently appreciates a wide variety of foreign cuisines and real dining experiences.

Banglalink Travel International Ltd decided to offer culinary tourism packages to existing customers while also generating a new client segment to help boost culinary tourism in Bangladesh. This study focuses on the client perceptions of Banglalink Travels International Ltd.'s planned culinary tourist packages.

1.3- Objective of the Study

The objectives of the proposed study are as follows:

The Main Objective

- To understand the role of travel agencies in the rise of culinary tourism.

The Specific Objective

- To identify the market segment of culinary tourism, including customer expectations, knowledge, and concerns in Bangladesh, through the study of “Banglalink Travels International Ltd.”
- To gain a better understanding of the culinary tourism packages in Bangladesh.

1.4- Rationale of the Study

The tourism industry is not a modern-day discovery. Tourism has been happening since ancient times. In the olden days, people used to travel to visit friends and family, religious purposes. From ancient times till this date, tourism has taken many forms, such as Business tourism, Agritourism, Culinary tourism, etc. Many tourists are the modern form of the tourism sector. Culinary tourism is one of them. It is creating a new segment of customers in the tourism industry nowadays. It is becoming the focus point for travelers to have a distinct motive to travel, which is related to food, except for the traditional goals of travelling.

Many tour operators and travel agencies are planning to grab this opportunity created by the culinary tourism itinerary. Like other tour operators and travel agencies, Banglalink Travels International Ltd is planning to provide its best effort to offer the first-ever culinary tourism package by any travel agency in Bangladesh to its existing customers and potential customers.

1.5- Scope of the Study

Documenting the potential of culinary tourism practices in Bangladesh by two operators and travel agencies was the aim of the report. I have only researched Bangladesh's tourism and travel industry's current trends. I now have a better understanding of how to present trendy travel packages from a Bangladeshi standpoint thanks to this research. This inquiry also provides me with information regarding the booking system, packaging, ticketing, and visa preparation services offered by Banglalink Travels International Ltd. in Bangladesh. I now have a better knowledge of Bangladesh's travel agency market and the possibility of Banglalink Travels International Ltd operating there thanks to my research.

1.6- Limitations of the study

Finding a variety of information about the company is really challenging for a researcher. As a result, I encountered a number of problems while researching the business. Gathering a variety of data for a thesis paper that must be finished in three months is challenging.

As a result, one of the most important impediments to studying is time. Other specific constraints include:

- There are several restrictions when conducting any type of activity straight to the top management level.
- Data is not available in a systematic manner.
- The company may be unwilling to disclose information to the intern.
- Some consumers were uncooperative in filling out the form, while others were unpleasant when I asked them questions.
- My survey sample was limited to within the organization due to time constraints and a lack of human resources.
- Because this is my first time preparing a study of this nature, a lack of experience is one of the study's significant limitations.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

According to Dr. M. M. N. Absar et al. (2010), travel and tourism have grown in importance to the global economy over the last few years. In 2012, Abscar, M. M. N. The tourism industry is one of the largest and fastest-growing areas of the global economy, with many small and medium-sized businesses striving to prosper in a highly competitive and dynamic business climate. According to Elena et al. (2012), one of the most lucrative industries in Bangladesh is tourism. According to (Absar, Mir Mohammed Nurul & Mohmood, 2011), this location has long been known for its breathtaking beauty. Foreign visitors commended the country's natural beauty, cultural richness, and welcoming population (Jahangir, 1998).

According to Pennington and Thomsen (2010), Bangladesh's share of total arrivals in South Asia is significantly underrepresented. According to (N. Absar et al., 2012), Bangladesh is an Asian country with high tourism potential. Bangladesh has been a popular travel destination for many years. Her status, however, is now marginal in terms of international travel.

Tourism contributes to the immediate development of a country's infrastructure, benefiting both tourists and locals. Tourism stimulates a destination country's infrastructure as well as other physical assets. Furthermore, tourism has the potential to be an effective tool for poverty reduction in developing countries. Tourism has a variety of direct and indirect benefits for the underprivileged. Furthermore, it can provide opportunities for long-term income, cultural pride, and a sense of ownership, as well as reduced vulnerability through diversification and the development of poor people's unique abilities (WTO, 2002). Even while tourism has many positive consequences on the economy, society, and environment, especially in rural areas and poor countries, mass tourism has been connected to detrimental outcomes.

Roy & Roy (2015), Although there are many economic, social, and environmental benefits to tourism, especially in rural areas and developing countries, mass tourism has been associated with drawbacks. He has shown that the variety of tourist locations makes a tourism strategy beneficial to the economy. Choy & Kamoche (2020) showed that the country has a favorable trend in arrivals and profits, which may be enhanced to a large level if proper promotion methods are implemented and the budget for this purpose is increased. In addition, the government must engage innovative individuals for this goal, and the quality of promotional materials must be improved.

According to ATLAS (2016), the expansion of the service industry will accelerate our economic growth. In light of Vision 2021, the study established a variety of competitive strategies that resulted in long-term economic growth. Redwan (2014) emphasized the importance of tourism in Bangladesh as well as its benefits in terms of socioeconomic development. Tourism has numerous benefits, including GDP contribution, job creation, foreign currency earnings, infrastructure development, investment opportunities, poverty alleviation, government revenue, and cultural development. Shamsuddoha and Chowdhury talked about how this industry has a number of potential ways to make money both domestically and abroad. They offered BPC a number of crucial suggestions for expanding the tourism industry. Jithendran & Baum (2000) demonstrated how the significance of tourism is analyzed from a number of angles, including political, social, cultural, and economic. Currently, less than 1% of our GDP comes from tourism. Raising it to 5% would result in the creation of almost 5,000 direct and indirect employment, increasing the economic index across the board. Ashraful, Khandakar, and Pangil (2019) calculated that using a conceptual model, it is possible to grasp the tourist sector's leaks and injections, as well as their true impact on the economy as a whole. According to Mahmood & Absar (2015), improving the efficiency and efficacy of tourism sector services, setting up better amenities, cost-cutting strategies, technical advancements, and infrastructure development can all encourage both domestic and foreign tourists to travel for various alternative reasons.

As stated by the mentioned respondents, RASAL & al NAIEM (2021) examined that this report assesses the current growth and development of this industry as well as some of its limitations and obstacles and offers some legislative solutions to overcome the industry's current obstacles. Saha (2020) investigated several aspects of tourism marketing strategies. According to the author, tourism should be viewed as a crucial part of the nation's economic development, and the marketing strategy and its implementation should work together. An integrated marketing communications channel should be put in place in order to grow the nation's tourism industry. According to The Daily Star (2014), tourism marketing is a concerted effort to give visitors the best services available. It's a device that converts prospective travelers into paying clients.

Chapter 3: Organizational Profile

3.1-Background of the Tour Operator of Bangladesh

In 1992, the Tour Operators Association (TOAB) of Bangladesh was established. A few tour companies in Bangladesh saw the need for a trade association or group to assist them in overcoming the numerous problems and challenges they frequently encountered during this period. Aside from that, the organization's primary goals were to market Bangladeshi tourism products abroad and to promote and boost tourism in Bangladesh. The People's Republic of Bangladesh's Ministry of Commerce officially recognized the association as a trade organization in 2002 following a protracted wait and the completion of the required procedures. As of right moment, TOAB has 751 active members.

Whether traveling for business or pleasure, tourists around the world have pretty high expectations for risk-free travel, safe food and lodging, quick site visits, and an economically cost-effective transaction at every level. Tour operators show up to meet the demands of a single traveler or a group of tourists, and they offer all necessary services. They serve as a one-stop shop for both domestic and foreign tourists, whether they are traveling within or beyond the nation. Travelers are advised to book their vacation through a TOAB member since it is safer and more genuine due to Bangladesh's poor tourist infrastructure.

The main objective of TOAB is to promote foreign tourists to Bangladesh's tourist destinations and establishments while simultaneously working to enhance domestic travel. Since its establishment, TOAB has put up endless effort to boost domestic tourism by encouraging foreign tourists to visit Bangladesh's tourist destinations. Ninety percent of tour activities in Bangladesh are the responsibility of TOAB members. By generating foreign cash from arriving tourists, they significantly contribute to Bangladesh's economic expansion. TOAB works successfully with the Ministry of Civil Aviation and Tourism, Bangladesh Parjatan Corporation, Bangladesh Tourism Board, FBCCI, and other tourism organizations. Since its establishment, TOAB has assisted BTB, BPC, and the Ministry with various policy-making procedures.

3.2-Background of the Travel Agency of Bangladesh

Soon after the nation was freed, travel agency owners felt obligated to band together under one roof, both to protect their financial interests and to support the healthy growth of Bangladesh's newly founded travel, tourist, and aviation industries. To achieve the intended purpose, travel agency owners from the time period assembled at the Dhaka Club in December 1976 to form the "IATA Travel Agents Association (ITAA)." On December 18, 1979, ATAB was registered with the Bangladeshi government under section 3(2)C of the Trade Organization Ordinance, 1961, and section 26 of the Companies Act, 1943. The Executive Committee of ATAB shall be chosen for a two-year term, according to the Constitution. The ATAB Tourist Training Institute (ATTI) was established in 2007 to provide competent personnel to the travel and tourism sector. Meanwhile, ATTI has certified around 2500 trainees who are presently employed at various companies, suggesting that ATTI is playing a vital role in the country's growth of skilled people.

ATAB is presently one of the most well-organized and well-known groups in the country, with over 3500 members. ATAB is seen as an important part of the aviation sector, with government authorities seeking its advice on a number of themes, including air travel, Hajj-Umrah, and other issues. ATAB had established itself as a prominent participant in Bangladesh's aviation and tourist industries by this time, allowing its founders' goals to come true.

Figure 1: Basic Organization Structure

3.3- Background of the organization

In Bangladesh, Banglalink Travels International Ltd. has developed into a well-known travel business. Clients inbound and leaving excursions are usually planned depending on their personality, status, test, and trend. Banglalink Travels International Ltd. is prepared to give a stress-free tour to its customers. Their primary objective is to organize a stress-free tour. It was founded in 2008. It was recognized by the Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, and its headquarters are located in Dewanhat, Chattogram. It welcomes guests from both the United States and other countries. Bangladeshi tour and travel businesses provide air ticketing services for both domestic and foreign carriers. Banglalink Travels International Ltd., like other travel agencies, makes hotel reservations on behalf of customers internationally. Customers may get entire packages from the organization that include assistance, transportation, meals, and lodging, all of which are reliable and secure.

3.2- Vision

By 2030, Banglalink Travels International Ltd. wants to be a market leader **by delivering higher- quality** service and digital public offers and creating many modern tourism markets.

3.3- Mission

The goal of the organization is to provide a service for those who like travelling. We are dedicated to offering unrivalled travel solutions, especially HR-related solutions, to customers travelling throughout the world.

3.4- Services

Banglalink Travels International Ltd. is a tour and travel firm that offers tour and travel services while being directed by experts in order to achieve the goal of tourism and honesty in our nation. As a Bangladeshi travel agency, Banglalink Travels International Ltd. offers a variety of services to domestic and foreign travelers.

3.4.1- Air Ticket:

Banglalink Travels International Ltd. Offers Airline tickets:

1. Tickets for International Flights.

3.4.2- Package Tours

Banglalink Travels International Ltd. provides travelers with both international solo, group, specialized, and customized tour options. This company can provide a consumer with a desired visit package at a reasonable cost.

3.4.3- Hotel Reservation

Banglalink Travels International Ltd. not only sells plane tickets, but they also book hotels overseas. It has over 4000 hotels in over 100 cities worldwide.

3.4.4- Visa Processing Services

Banglalink Travels International Ltd. provides experienced advice to make visa applications easier. It is necessary to provide precise and basic information in order to complete a visa application. Banglalink Travels International Ltd. has a success rate of greater than 90%. Banglalink Travels International Ltd. provides visa services to the following countries: India, Thailand, Malaysia, Singapore, Bhutan, Nepal, Vietnam, Sri Lanka, Maldives, Dubai, and Saudi Arabia.

3.4.5- Other Concurrent Services

- Airport Transfer
- Excursion
- Rail and bus tickets

3.4.6- Services with unique features

Our goal has been to create a one-of-a-kind and amazing travel experience that fulfills our clients' actual desires since the beginning of the firm. While providing you with the best value, the company provides this service with expertise, knowledge, and innovation.

Chapter 4: Travel Agency and Culinary Tourism Market

4.1- Insight into Culinary Tourism

Culinary tourism is a new field of academic research. Long (2004) first referred to the term “Culinary Tourism” in 1998 to express the idea of experiencing other cultures through food. Wolf explained culinary tourism as the combination of travelling, exploration, and enjoyment of food and drinks with gastronomic/ Culinary experiences.

According to Dr. Prem, Author of “A Complete Guide to Culinary Tourism,” Culinary Tourism in his book as a wonderful departure from what we usually eat at home. Culinary tourism is also the process by which a destination tries to seek maximum economic potential through its local food culture and tradition through tourism-related services.

Bob McKercher in “Food Tourism as a Viable Market Segment: It's all how You Cook the Numbers!”, Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing, 2008, described “Food is believed to rank alongside climate, accommodation and scenery in importance to tourists.”

4.1.1- History of Culinary Tourism

Year	Events
1998	Long referred to the term “Culinary Tourism”
2001	Erik Wolf, the President of the International Culinary Tourism Association (ICTA), launched a white paper about culinary tourism.
2012	The World Food Travel Association stopped using the term “Culinary Tourism” because various researchers revealed it as a misleading impression.

Figure 2: History Chart of Culinary Tourism

4.1.2- Evaluation of Other Culinary Tourism Terms:

Terms	Events
Food Tourism	After the World Food Travel Association stopped using “Culinary Tourism”
Gastronomy Tourism	As culinary tourism grew, Gastronomy Tourism also came into light as European people thought “Food Tourism” sounded very basic and had no cultural significance to it.

Figure 3: Evaluation of Terms

4.2- Starting of Culinary Tourism

While on a trip, travellers tend to test the unique flavour of the food at the tourist place. They have in mind to experience the local food culture and tradition.

4.2.1- Culinary Tourism & International Aspect

Based on the uniqueness of culinary culture, lifestyle, and tradition, different regions, states, and countries offer different kinds of food. A specific cuisine represents the country it originated from, and Fusion Food represents the food and flavour from mixing two or more cuisines.

Name of Country	Famous Food
Japan	Sushi, Sea Weeds, Fish
Middle East and North African Countries	Kebabs, Lamb, Date Puddings, Pita Bread
American Cuisine	Steaks of Medium and Rare Cook
German	Chocolate, Cakes, Sauerkraut
Korean	Dog Dish
Myanmar	Nappi

Figure 4: Some of the Most Famous Foods from Several Countries

Some of the Most Popular Culinary Festivals around the World

Name of Country	Name of Festival	Time of Celebration	Place of Celebration
India	“The Spring Food Festival”	February	Lajpat Bhawan, Delhi
	“Goa Food and Cultural Festival “	February (3days Festival)	Goa
Mexico	“Three Kings Festival”	6 th January	Major Cities in Mexico
	“Ice Cream Festival”	March (127 Years Old Fair)	Tulyehualco, Mexico
Vietnam	“Tet Han Thuc” (Cold Foods Festival)	-----	----- ----
Peru	“Mistura Food Festival”	September	Lima
Italy	“Pizzafest”	September (10day Festival)	Naples (Birthplace of Pizza)
	“I’Primi D’Italia, Foligno”	September (3 days Festival)	
United States	“New York City Wine & Food Festival”	October	New York
Canada	“Caribana Festival”	Two Weeks in the Summer	Canada
Ireland	“Taste of Dublin”	May	-----
	“Burren Slow Food Festival”	June	-----

Figure 5: Some of the Most Popular Culinary Festivals around the World

Countries Promoting Culinary Tourism:

- Mexico
- France
- India

- Italy
- Thailand
- San Diego, California
- Vietnam
- Caribbean Island

4.3- Essential Components of Culinary Tourism

- Availability of Natural Resources
 - Nurturing and Cultivating Local Resources and Culinary Tradition
 - Decent Eating Places and Dining Culture
 - Awareness of the Local People
 - Accessibility and Cost
 - Destination Management Organization
 - Tourism & Travel Arrangements

4.3.1- Culinary Tourism Value Chain

Figure 6: Benefit from the Development of Food Tourism

4.4- Culinary Tourism Market

The culinary tourism market is estimated to grow at a CAGR of 17.45% and the size of the market is forecast to increase by USD 126.28 billion between 2022 and 2027.

Figure 7: Culinary Tourism Market Size Outlook

4.4.1- Culinary Tourism Market Segmentation

❖ By Application

Figure 8: Culinary Tourism Market by Application

❖ **By Product**

Figure 9: Culinary Tourism Market by Product

❖ **By Geographic Location**

Figure 10: Culinary Tourism Market by Geographic Location

4.4.2- Major Culinary Tourism Market Vendor

- Gourmet on Tour Ltd
- Greaves Travel Ltd
- Heritage Group
- India Food Tour
- International Culinary Tours
- Lindblad Expeditions Holding Inc
- The FTC4Lobe Corp
- Top Deck Tour Ltd
- TourRadar GmbLt
- ITC Ltd

4.5- Culinary Tourism Market and Travel Agency

Figure 11: Market Contribution of Various Segments in Culinary Tourism

Travel agency involvement in culinary tourism packages is the most important factor. The role of travel agencies in creating a market for culinary tourism packages can ease the way for the development of culinary tourism, not only domestically but also internationally. Banglalink Travels International Ltd always ensures the best packages and tourism services for the customer. Banglalink Travels International Ltd. keeps up to date with the trend. Whenever a tourism form or activity is in trend, it works with the trend to give the customer its best services to create customer relationships and loyalty.

During the modern trend of culinary tourism in Bangladesh, Banglalink Travels International Ltd also understood the trend and potential for culinary tourism and its contribution to the economic and overall development of Bangladesh. To keep up with the trend, Banglalink Travels International Ltd decided to launch an upcoming culinary tourism package for its existing customers and create potential customers.

4.5.1- Process of Launching the Upcoming Culinary Tourism Packages:

Figure 12: Process of Launching the Upcoming Culinary Tourism Packages by Banglalink Travels International Ltd

Chapter 5: Methodology of the Study

5.1- Research Design

For my investigation, I used a quantitative approach. For this, I've set up a well-organized survey to collect data from respondents. Individuals who are related to Banglalink Travels International Ltd., especially employees and members of the governing body. For the purpose of completing the study, I have created a questionnaire to collect data from a target sample.

5.2- Source of Data

For the investigation, I used both primary and secondary data.

5.2.1-Primary Sources

The following are some of the primary sources-

- Consultation with the administrators,
- Direct interaction with staff and visitors.

5.2.2-Secondary sources

The secondary data are those that have already been obtained and put through the fact-checking process. The following are some more resources-

- Various books and periodicals
- Source on the web

- Report on previous audits

5.3- Population Selection

The population on which the study was conducted mainly comprised individuals who are related to Banglalink Travels International Ltd., especially employees and members of the governing body.

5.4- Sample Size Determination

The survey was conducted on 50 respondents. The majority of them are current customers who are connected with the organization, and also the administrators of the organization.

5.5- Methods of Data Collection

Data collection for the study was done primarily in two ways. First was the face-to-face counselling with the members of the governing body, and a questionnaire was used to collect data from the customers of “Banglalink Travel International Ltd.” regarding the respondents’ perception about Culinary Tourism packages.

5.6- Data Collection Instruments

The **questionnaire** that was developed to collect the responses of the target respondents regarding the respondents’ perception aspect of the study is attached in the appendix part of the report.

5.7- Data Analysis Techniques

To analyze the response from the questionnaire survey, I used MS Word, MS Excel, and other computer software related to data analysis.

Chapter 6: Analysis and Major Findings

To determine the survey's outcome, a systematic questionnaire is created. A total of 50 participants were polled for this study. This group contains primarily Banglalink Travels International Ltd customers. MS Excel is being used to evaluate the data. I'll describe the findings and analysis that I discovered using the questionnaire in this section.

Demographic Profile & Interest

- **Gender:** The results are listed below-

▪ **Age:**

▪ **Frequency of Travel**

▪ **Idea about Culinary Tourism**

▪ **Interest in Culinary Tourism Packages**

▪ **Perception about the Involvement of Travel Agencies in the Rise of the Culinary Tourism**

▪ **Attraction towards Different Cuisines**

▪ **Demand for Tourism Services**

▪ **Concern about Culinary Tourism Packages**

▪ Demand for several packages

Chapter 7: Problems and Recommendations of Culinary Tourism Packages

7.1 Problems or Challenges Faced by Banglalink Travel International Ltd for the Upcoming Culinary Tourism Packages

For the upcoming Culinary Tourism packages, Banglalink Travel International Ltd is facing some challenges. During the survey of customers' perception about Culinary Tourism Packages, Banglalink Travels International Ltd found out some issues involved in the launching of culinary tourism packages, not only related to customers, but also some issues are major inside the organizations and the tourism market. Here are those issues:

- Half of the current customers of Banglalink Travels International Ltd are interested in culinary tourism packages, while the other half is concerned about budgets, as Banglalink Travels International Ltd didn't highlight anything about the expected budget for the upcoming package, and some of the customers are budget-conscious.
- 25% customers don't have any idea about the involvement of the travel agency in the rise of culinary tourism. Lack of knowledge.
- Some customers were confused whether these culinary packages would be worth it or not, or if they would face boredom or uniformity.
- Banglalink Travels International Ltd only works with international packages for native people, but especially for culinary tourism packages; they also feel the need to work domestically.
- Absence of knowledgeable and trained Human Resources about culinary tourism and its ins and outs in the agency.
- Not having any previous standard for culinary tourism packages in Bangladesh.

7.2 Recommendations for Banglalink Travels International Ltd for the Upcoming Culinary Tourism Packages

I would like to make some recommendations based on the data and analysis of this study to enhance Banglalink Travel International Ltd.'s upcoming culinary tourism packages.

- As many customers are not interested in the culinary tourism packages, Banglalink Travels International Ltd can make interesting packages and make the information available to those not interested. That may attract them to the upcoming package.
- As half of the people who are interested in the culinary tourism packages are concerned about the budget of the packages, Banglalink Travels International Ltd should make the budget affordable for the budget-conscious customer segment.
- Many of their customers have no idea about culinary tourism. Not only for those customers but also for creating awareness about culinary tourism, Banglalink Travels International Ltd can make a promotional campaign. Their online site is much boosted, so they should make an online campaign about the package.
- As people of Bangladesh and also from foreign countries are interested in Bangladeshi local food cuisine, and this would make way easier to reach people about culinary tourism packages domestically and internationally, Banglalink Travels International Ltd should focus on working domestically and offer packages for domestic culinary tourism. They will be able to reach the international culinary tourism target market from Bangladesh through the domestic market.
- Fresher's or graduates majoring in Tourism & Hospitality Management should be recruited as they have up-to-date knowledge about the tourism trend and the modern form of tourism as Culinary Tourism.
- As Banglalink Travels International Ltd is the first agency to launch culinary tourism packages, they don't have any previous standard. That's a problem for them because standards tell us the destination we need to reach. For this, Banglalink Travels International can slide into international travel agencies offering culinary tourism packages and their standard way of operation, and all.

Chapter 8: Conclusion

Travel agencies promote Bangladeshi culture as well as the tourism sector around the world. There are several opportunities in our country, and tour and travel companies can take advantage of them to grow their enterprises and reach their desired goals. The tourism business is now the fastest-expanding industry in the world. The tourism industry has grown dramatically around the world as a result of tourist visits and currency exchange, creating competition between countries and propelling tourism to the top of the global priority list.

Banglalink Travels International Ltd is a company that specializes in providing transportation services and offering new packages to its customers to do the tourism business. They must meet a slew of objectives in order to establish a foothold in the market. By looking into everything needed for the success of culinary tourism packages and other packages, and also taking needed decisions in time, can make Banglalink Travels International Ltd topper of the top tour operator and travel agency business in Bangladesh. It is possible to conclude that these tactics will assist them in achieving their desired objectives, and that they are also quite adaptable, allowing them to adapt to changing market conditions and secure a favorable position in the culinary tourism market, problems & solutions of the marketplace. Banglalink Travels International Ltd provides economical and, in specific cases, VIP services to its consumers, and the majority of them are pleased with them, stating that the services are of high quality and that they are provided at a reasonable cost. Banglalink Travels International Ltd. does everything it can for its customers so that they are never dissatisfied when they arrive at their workplace. They lighten up their workspace, put up a nice setting, and create a pleasant atmosphere.

Finally, I'd like to note that my report fulfils a portion of the requirements for my university work, and all of the concerns and recommendations listed below are based on my research. All of the observations were made from my point of view; thus, they can't be utilized to make policy; however, if a company wants to, they may evaluate the entire research from the start. The market has become extremely competitive. With the aid of business, everyone may succeed in life. Banglalink Travels International Ltd is a tour operator. I'm hoping they can establish a good reputation by delivering high-quality travel services through their travel business and make their foothold also in the culinary tourism market.

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Appendix

Survey Questionnaire:

Customer Survey on Upcoming Culinary Tour Packages by Banglalink Travels International Ltd

I'm Ispita Nag, working on the report of "The Role of Travel Agency in the Rise of Culinary Tourism". Culinary Tourism is creating a new market segment day by day. For the increasing demand for this modern tourism, Banglalink Travels International Ltd decided to launch Culinary Tourism packages. So, this survey is for customer perception survey based on the upcoming tourism packages.

Demographic Profile and Interest

Name:

Age:

Fill in the circle on your response sheet that best represents your point of view to indicate how much you agree or disagree with each statement. Please select an answer from the list below.

1) Gender:

- Male
- Female
- Prefer not to say
- Third Gender
- Transgender

2) Age:

- 15-25
- 25-35
- 35-45
- 45-55
- 55-more

3) How frequently do you travel in a year?

- Once
- Twice
- Weekly
- Monthly
- More Than That

4) Do you have any idea about Culinary/Gastronomy/Food Tourism?

- Yes
- No

5) If so, from where did you get the idea about Culinary Tourism?

- Social Media
- Friends & Family
- Book
- Others.....

6) If Banglalink Travels International Ltd offers packages for Culinary Tourism in the Future, how interested will you be?

- Highly Interested
- Interested
- Neutral
- Less Interested
- No Interest

7) Do you think the involvement of the Travel Agency in the rise of Culinary Tourism is needed?

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

8) Do you think the Travel Agency would ease the way for Culinary Tourism?

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

9) Travel Agency makes a new target market along with the existing target market in Culinary Tourism?

- Yes
- No
- Maybe

10) Which Cuisine attracts you the most?

- Indian
- French
- Spanish
- Italian
- Chinese
- Mexican
- Thai
- Vietnamese
- Turkish
- Others:

11) What types of tourism services do you want from Banglalink Travels International Is Ltd.'s Culinary Tourism Packages?

- Ticket
- Accommodation
- Short Culinary Training
- Food Expedition
- Sightseeing
- Transfer Facilities
- Others:

12) What kind of packages do you want for Culinary Tourism by Banglalink Travels International Ltd?

- Independent
- Group
- Customized

13) In Culinary Tourism packages, you are concerned about-

- Safety & Security
- Budget
- Boredom
- Not Worthy
- Others:

14) Any recommendations for Banglalink Travel International Ltd for their upcoming Culinary Tourism packages?